

Determination of Specific Absorption Rate from Mobile Phones on Active Call Within Sokoto Metropolis, Northwest, Nigeria

Sadiya Umar^{1*} and N. N. Garba²

¹Department of Physics, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

²Department of Physics, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria

Corresponding Author: Sadiya.umar@udusok.edu.ng 07039638408

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18171063>

Abstract

Mobile phone technology has brought important benefits to individuals, businesses, and society. Like most technologies, there are negative effects that can arise as a result of using radiofrequency (RF) radiation source from mobile phones. Health effects can arise as a result of exposure to this radiation. In this study, power density and electromagnetic fields from mobile phones were measured using a handheld electromagnetic field meter GQ EMF 390. Measurements were obtained from some sources of electromagnetic field (EMF) from mobile phone users on active calls. The power density and electromagnetic field values were used to obtain the specific absorption rate of radiation in tissue (SAR). The highest value of SAR obtained was 0.0027 W/kg. the maximum value obtained is lower than the maximum recommended limit of 0.08 W/kg of tissue. Therefore, radio frequency radiation emissions from the selected mobile phones on active calls are within the maximum permissible exposure limit set by International Commission on Non-ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP).

Keywords: Radiation, Radiofrequency, exposure, specific absorption rate, mobile phones.

INTRODUCTION

Cell phone technology which includes the use of base transceiver stations, cell phones, WIFI and Bluetooth devices has revolutionized the telecommunication industry in Nigeria. Due to its advantages, mobile phone technology has grown exponentially in the last decade. Presently, there exist more than 6.9 billion mobile subscriptions globally and over 1.4 million mobile base transceiver stations (BTS) exist worldwide to meet the growing communication demand and the number is increasing significantly. The Global System of Mobile (GSM) communication has proved to be of tremendous benefit to the society especially in a developing country like Nigeria, where other forms of communication exist to a very limited extent. Nigeria is the largest mobile telecommunications market in Africa, largely based on rapid development following the successful auction of Digital Mobile Licenses (DML) in 2001 (NCC, 2019) (NNBP, 2020). According to the Nigerian Communication Commissions (NCC) annual report, mobile subscribers increased with a total of 27, 811,580, from 145,059,514 subscribers in 2017 to record high of 172,871,094 active voice subscriptions as at December 2018. By December 2019, the market served over 184 million Mobile lines, with 126 Million of those lines connected to Internet services (NCC, 2019). Today we are exposed to 100 million times more EMFs than our grandparents were (Girish, 2010). That's because most of the trappings of modern life – appliances, cell phones, wireless Internet, and more – emit artificial EMFs that disrupt the body's natural energy field and can cause many health problems. The more EMFs to which we are exposed, the more likely and serious your risk is. there were several reports that the electromagnetic radiation released by mobile telecommunications, which includes the use of cell phones, Wi-Fi and Bluetooth devices has now become the main man-made source of environmental radiation

The negative effects of non-ionizing radiation have been reported and the unwillingness of the cell phone companies to admit in public the results and to be responsible for the impacts this technology has in the human body is worrisome. The awareness of effects of radiofrequency emitted can educate the public on the consequences of using these RF sources for a long period of time.

Because of these aforementioned problems this work was carried out in order to check radiation exposure from the selected mobile phones, and to determine whether or not radiation emissions from these devices exceed the standard safety exposure limits.

Therefore, the aim of this work is to determine the specific absorption rate of some selected mobile phones within Sokoto metropolis.

Owoh and his team carried out a study to examine the possible potential health risks that result from the use of some commonly available mobile phones in Nigeria. The mobile phones subjected to test were Tecno S1, Touching T1, Infinix hot 6 and Itel 1701. Their electric field strength, magnetic field strength and power density varied significantly per call engagement mode at various varied distances of measurement. Also, their computed head SAR values were observed to be below the limit set by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection. From a potential health hazard point of view, Tecno S1 was found to be the safest for use (Owoh *et al.*, 2020)

Khuzairi *et al* (2019) mentioned that the usage of mobile phone as a communication medium and information source are becoming ubiquitous in this era in Malaysia. It is to be understood that the radiation emitted from the antenna mounted on BTS is a type of non-ionizing radiation. There are invalid and insignificant evidence to support the claims that the radiation could cause adverse health effect to the human. The findings in his research were based on the indoor and outdoor measurement which shows that the level of E-field strength is very low. Furthermore, the finding in this research suggests that the usage of mobile phone from 2G, 3G, Wi-Fi for indoor and fourth generation mobile network (4G) and the BTS in Pulau Pinang will also be safe for the public, due to the radiation level at this particular location adheres to the permitted exposure limit.

Bhat (2013) in his work titled - Effects of Electromagnetic Waves Emitted by Mobile Phones On Male Fertility. reported that there are health effects that can occur when the human body is exposed to high levels of radio frequency (RF) energy, and Microwave radiation causes increase in tissue temperature. Riki *et al* (2015) in their work titled – Mobile Effect on Human Body . reported that the electromagnetic radiation emitted by mobile phones and towers are harmful, so people should keep away from the transmission towers and persons should use mobile phone as soon as low timing.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Measurement Procedure

Mobile phones uses 2G and 3G Network that emit RF frequency radiation in the range of of 900 MHz to 1800 MHz when used to make calls. In this study mobile phones were used to obtain data for phone on active call. Fifty (50) different mobile phones selected at random from different active users within a higher institution of learning from Sokoto metropolis. Fifty (50) measurements were obtained when phone is on active call engagement. Measurements were taken using GQ EMF 390 V-2 capable of measuring power density, electric field and magnetic field in different units. EMF has Zero Calibration. The data were obtained by pointing the EMF meter in front of each mobile phone. The measurements were obtained at 0 cm distance from the phone at one second interval for a period of one minute from each of the mobile phone used in the study. The EMF meter was placed directly on the phone for direct contact with the skin since most of the time the phone is either held on the hand or place on the ear thereby having direct

contact with skin. Each mobile phone was placed on a laboratory stand as shown in Plate I. The phones on active calls were labeled S1 to S50. The EMF results obtained were used to calculate the specific absorption rate (SAR) to tissue of the human body.

Plate I: Mobile phone EMF measurement using GQ EMF 390

Data Processing and analysis

Random sampling was used to select the cell phones. Data used in this study involved both primary and secondary data. The secondary data were collected from records of the ICNIRP, NCC, FCC and WHO recommended guidelines while the primary data was collected through field measurement. The data collected were used to analyze power density, EMF and SAR of radiation which was used to check if the exposure levels in these RF sources are low and as such not able to produce significant health risks among the people using the mobile phones.

Specific Absorption Rate

Specific absorption rate (SAR) is used to describe the rate of radio frequency radiation (RFR) energy absorbed in a unit of tissue in the body. It is expressed in Watt per kilogram (W/kg) of tissue. SAR is usually averaged over the whole body or over small volume tissue typically between 1 and 10 g of tissue. SAR has more authenticity to determine the biological effect of radio frequency radiations (RFR's) than power density, since SAR reflects what is really being absorbed by matter rather than the energy in space.

$$\text{SAR} = (\sigma * |E|^2) / \rho \quad 1$$

Where σ is the electrical conductivity of the skin tissue ($1/\Omega\text{m}$), ρ is the density of skin tissue (Kg/m^3), and E is the electric field inside the material (Girish, 2010).

In this study, the measured Electric field from mobile phone was used to calculate the specific absorption rate for human skin tissue using equation 1 where

$$\sigma = 0.872 (1/\Omega\text{m}), \text{ and } \rho = 1100 \text{ Kg}/\text{m}^3$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of all the measured power density, electromagnetic fields, and calculated specific absorption rate obtained at 0cm distance for 50 mobile phones on active call are presented in Table 1. The measured electric field was used to calculate the SAR for skin tissue using equation 1. The reason for using skin tissue is to show direct contact of mobile radiation with the body since the skin is the first point of contact through which the radiofrequency radiation is absorbed by the body. The value of the maximum power density was found to be 3.585 mWm^{-2} observed for mobile phone S31 while the minimum power density was found to be 0.001 mWm^{-2} at S23

and S34. The maximum power density of be 3.585 mWm^{-2} obtained is below the ICNIRP maximum permissible limit of 4.7 Wm^{-2} as indicated in the standard guidelines.

Table 1: Electromagnetic fields, Power density, and Specific absorption rate

S/NO	mG	V/m	mW/m ²	Conductivity, δ (1/ Ωm)	ass Density, ρ (Kg/m ³)	E ²	δE^2	$\delta\text{E}^2/\rho$
1	0.7	1.1	0.02	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
2	0.8	1.1	0.005	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
3	0.9	1.1	0.016	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
4	0.9	1.1	0.004	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
5	0.9	1.4	0.015	0.872	1100	1.96	1.70912	0.001554
6	0.8	1.1	0.015	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
7	0.9	1.1	0.008	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
8	0.7	0.8	0.007	0.872	1100	0.64	0.55808	0.000507
9	0.8	1	1.263	0.872	1100	1	0.872	0.000793
10	0.7	1.1	0.017	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
11	0.8	1.5	0.007	0.872	1100	2.25	1.962	0.001784
12	1	1.1	0.009	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
13	0.9	1.3	0.009	0.872	1100	1.69	1.47368	0.00134
14	0.9	1.1	0.002	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
15	0.8	1.1	0.014	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
16	0.6	1.2	0.003	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
17	0.8	1.2	0.002	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
18	0.7	0.8	0.004	0.872	1100	0.64	0.55808	0.000507
19	0.7	1.4	0.008	0.872	1100	1.96	1.70912	0.001554
20	0.8	1.4	0.009	0.872	1100	1.96	1.70912	0.001554
21	0.8	1.3	0.002	0.872	1100	1.69	1.47368	0.00134
22	0.9	1.1	0.006	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
23	0.9	1.1	0.001	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
24	0.8	1.3	0.017	0.872	1100	1.69	1.47368	0.00134
25	0.9	1.1	0.002	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
26	0.7	1	0.001	0.872	1100	1	0.872	0.000793
27	0.6	1	0.006	0.872	1100	1	0.872	0.000793

28	0.8	1.1	0.011	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
29	0.7	0.8	1.196	0.872	1100	0.64	0.55808	0.000507
30	0.7	1	0.001	0.872	1100	1	0.872	0.000793
31	0.8	1.2	3.585	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
32	0.8	1.2	0.008	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
33	1.4	1.5	0.004	0.872	1100	2.25	1.962	0.001784
34	0.9	1.1	0.001	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
35	0.7	1.1	0.009	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
36	0.9	1.1	0.015	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
37	0.9	1.1	0.009	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
38	0.9	1.3	0.015	0.872	1100	1.69	1.47368	0.00134
39	0.8	1.2	0.007	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
40	0.9	1.4	1.354	0.872	1100	1.96	1.70912	0.001554
41	0.8	0.8	0.017	0.872	1100	0.64	0.55808	0.000507
42	0.8	1.2	0.005	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
43	1	1.1	0.007	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
44	0.7	1.2	0.007	0.872	1100	1.44	1.25568	0.001142
45	0.8	1.5	0.005	0.872	1100	2.25	1.962	0.001784
46	0.9	1.1	0.008	0.872	1100	1.21	1.05512	0.000959
47	0.7	1	0.009	0.872	1100	1	0.872	0.000793
48	0.7	1.6	0.008	0.872	1100	2.56	2.23232	0.002029
49	0.7	0.4	0.005	0.872	1100	0.16	0.13952	0.000127
50	1	1.9	0.005	0.872	1100	3.61	3.14792	0.002862

Figure 1: Measured electromagnetic fields from Phones on active calls

Figure 1 shows the results of electric fields and magnetic fields obtained from mobile cell phones on active calls. It was observed that the highest electric field obtained was 1.9 V/m at S50 and the lowest was 0.4 V/m at S49 and for magnetic field the maximum value was 1.4 mG at S33 and lowest was 0.6 mG at S27 and S16 . All these EM field values are within the safety limits. The results showed that the EF radiation obtained from the mobile phones on active call are very low when using mobile phones to make calls. The values fluctuate as a result of EMF obstruction by nearby objects and interference by other nearby EMF devices.

Figure 2: Specific absorption rate for mobile phone on active calls

Similarly, Figure 2 shows the result of specific absorption rate in watts per kilogram (W/kg) of skin tissue calculated for mobile phones during call operation. The highest value of SAR was found to be 0.0027 W/kg at S50 while the lowest level of SAR was found to be 0.0001 W/kg S49. The maximum SAR obtained is below the ICNIRP maximum permissible limit of 0.08 W/kg of skin tissue as indicated in the standard guidelines.

The maximum value of electric field obtained was 1.9 V/m, Pd was 3.85 mWm² and SAR was 0.002 W/kg. to compare the results with other research, we find that the 1.9 V/m is higher than 0.504 V/m obtained by Khuzairi *et al* (2019) but lower than result of Owoh *et al.*, (2020) who obtained electric field values that range from 0.97 V/m to 8.54 V/m and Pd of 250mWm⁻². Adding to this Bhat (2013) obtained SAR of 0.0018 W/kg. These small differences may be due to transmitting power of the phone antenna, phone antenna design, phone model, temperature and phone condition – high temperature and damaged phone antenna can affect radiation levels. Another factor that may affect the readings is the cell tower network strength in the specific location, battery level of phone. power management, and interference by other electromagnetic field equipment,

CONCLUSION

The highest SAR obtained in this study is about 0.0027 W/kg of skin tissue. This indicates that the radio frequency radiation emitted from the selected mobile phones on active calls does not exceed the maximum permissible exposure limits of 0.08 W/kg set by the International Commission on Non ionizing Radiation Protection. Therefore, mobile phone use on active call engagement does not pose any significant health risk to people using it.

Avoidance is the best way to remove radiation exposure from our daily lives but these sources of RF are important in our daily lives, and the benefit outweighs the risk. Therefore, applying the ALARA principle, it is advisable to keep the use of mobile phone for making calls to as low as reasonably achievable.

REFERENCES

- Bhat, M.A. (2013). —Effects of Electromagnetic Waves Emitted by Mobile Phones on Male Fertility,” *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems*, 4(3).
- Girish Kumar (2010). Advantages and Disadvantages of Cell Phone Technology. Report on Cell Tower Radiation. *Report sent to Department of Telecommunications, Delhi, India.*
- International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection ICNIRP. (2020). Guidelines for Limiting Exposure to Time-Varying Electric, Magnetic, and Electromagnetic Fields (up to 300 GHz). *Health Physics*. 74(4):494-522
- International Journal of Computer and Communication System Engineering (IJCCSE)*, Vol. 2 (5), 2015, 686-690. ISSN: 2312-769
- Khuzairi M. 1, H. A. Rahim², M. Abdulmalek³, M. Nazri M. Warip⁴ (2019) Radio frequency radiation measurement for base tower station safety compliances: a case study in Pulau Pinang Malaysia. *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics 2. Bioelectromagnetics* Vol. 8, No. 1, March 2019, pp. 150~157 ISSN: 2302-9285, DOI: 10.11591/eei.v8i1.1407 □ 150 <http://beei.org/index.php/EEI>
- Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC) (2019). *Statistics_2020_Subscriber-Network_Year_End_Report.pdf* (pp. 2–57). <https://www.ncc.gov.ng>
- NNBP Nigerian National Broadband Plan (2020) National Broadband Plan 2020 – 2025 Pp 12 – 16. Retrieved 16 March 2020 from <https://www.ncc.gov.ng>
- Owoh Ekpuk Brown, Kingsley Monday Udofia, Akaninyene Bernard Obot (2020) Electromagnetic Field Levels Associated with Selected Mobile Phones *J. Int. Environmental Application & Science*, Vol. 15(2): 62-67
- Riki H., Patel Hardik Modi, Chandubhai S Patel, Vrunda S. Patel (2015). Mobile Effect on Human Body

